

Conductometric Studies on the Precipitation of Sodium and Ammonium Diuranate

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The reaction between uranyl nitrate, on the one hand, and sodium or ammonium hydroxide, on the other, has been investigated conductometrically by applying monovariation method. Job's method of continued variation has also been found suitable for the study of insoluble sodium diuranate. Complete precipitation occurs at the stoichiometric point and the reverse reaction (sodium hydroxide constant, uranyl ion varying) can be used for the conductometric estimation of uranium in uranyl salts.

Unlike molybdenum and tungsten, uranium is known to yield insoluble diuranate on addition of alkali to a uranyl salt solution. Arfvedson¹ obtained ammonium diuranate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{U}_2\text{O}_7$, as a hydrated yellow powder by treating uranyl nitrate or chloride with excess of ammonia. The product, according to him, could be dried at 100° without change, but at a higher temperature it was resolved into nitrogen, ammonia, water, and uranic oxide. Berzelius² reported its sparing solubility in water. Stolba³ and Patera⁴ obtained sodium diuranate as its hexahydrate by addition of an excess of sodium hydroxide to a uranyl salt solution and drying the washed precipitate in air. According to Metzger and Heidelberger⁵ sodium diuranate of the composition $\text{Na}_2\text{U}_2\text{O}_7$, may actually be precipitated, but on washing with water to remove the excess of alkali, it gradually undergoes partial hydrolysis; so the pure sodium uranate obtained by adding sodium hydroxide to a solution of uranyl nitrate has the composition $\text{Na}_4\text{U}_2\text{O}_{17}$.

The present communication deals with the physico-chemical aspect of the precipitation of diuranate.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standardised aqueous solutions of uranyl nitrate, sodium hydroxide, and ammonium hydroxide were used for all the experiments. A Doran conductivity bridge with a dip type conductivity cell was used for measurements of conductance at 28° .

Precipitation of Sodium Diuranate.—Sodium diuranate was precipitated by mixing equimolecular solutions of uranyl nitrate and NaOH. Fig. 1 exhibits two curves, A and B, obtained when varying amounts of NaOH were added to a constant volume (5ml)

1. *Swenska Akad. Handl.*, 1822, 404; *Ann. Phil.*, 1824, 7, 253.
2. *Schweigger's J.*, 1825, 44, 191.
3. *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1864, 3, 74.
4. *Dingler's J.*, 1854, 132, 30; 1856, 141, 371.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 31, 1040.

of uranyl nitrate solution, following the monovariation method. Curve A corresponds to $M/20$ equimolecular solutions and curve B refers to $M/30$ equimolar solutions of the reactants. The same reaction, when studied in the reverse way, yielded two curves A and B in Fig. 2; curve A stands for $M/20$ and curve B for $M/30$ equimolar solutions.

FIG. 1. Precipitation of Na diuranate by monovariation method. Uranyl nitrate const., NaOH varying.

FIG. 2. Precipitation of Na diuranate by monovariation method. NaOH const., uranyl nitrate varying.

The author has observed earlier⁶ that Job's method of continued variation, hitherto applied for the investigation of complexes in solution, can also be used for studying the composition of insoluble compounds as efficiently as the titration procedure or monovariation method. In the present case also, use of $M/20$ and $M/30$ equimolar solutions of uranyl nitrate and NaOH yielded two curves, A and B, respectively, as shown in Fig. 2.

Precipitation of Ammonium Diuranate.—The operation was carried out by applying the monovariation method only, the procedure being the same as in the case of sodium diuranate. Fig. 4 shows the curves obtained when uranium is the constant component and ammonium hydroxide, the varying one. Fig. 5 contains the curves obtained in the reverse case. In both the figures curve A stands for $M/20$ equimolar solutions and curve B for $M/30$ solutions.

DISCUSSION

Addition of alkali to uranyl nitrate solution should cause the formation of uranyl hydroxide, $UO_2(OH)_2$, which is known to be amphoteric in nature and can also be represented as H_2UO_4 , uranic acid, or $UO_3 \cdot H_2O$. In the present case, however (Figs. 1 and 4), no break in the experimental curves is obtained corresponding to the addition of two equivalents of alkali to uranyl nitrate solution. An excess of alkali solution, however,

FIG. 3. Precipitation of Na diuranate by Job's method of continued variation.

FIG. 4. Precipitation of amm. diuranate by monovariation method. Uranyl nitrate const., NH₄OH varying.

FIG. 5. Precipitation of amm. diuranate by monovariation method. NH₄OH const., uranyl nitrate varying.

causes precipitation of sodium or ammonium diuranate at three equivalents of alkali. The reaction may be represented as:

Addition of the two steps gives

The precipitation of ammonium diuranate can be written in the same way as done in the above case.

It is to be noticed that the break in the experimental curves corresponding to the precipitation of diuranate occurs at the exact theoretical value (vide Figs. 1, 2, 4 & 5). Application of Job's method also yields curves with sharp maximum at 75% NaOH (Fig. 3), which is to be expected theoretically. According to the author's contention⁶ therefore the precipitate can be of importance in the quantitative estimation of uranyl salts. Though uranium is some times estimated gravimetrically as ammonium diuranate⁷, the precipitate has a tendency to become colloidal on washing. The reverse titration of uranyl nitrate with sodium hydroxide (Fig. 2) provides a sharp break at the exact stoichiometric ratio and hence this procedure can be of use for the estimation of uranium by a simple conductometric titration.

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